

PEDAGOGICAL SKILL AND COMPETENCE TOUCH

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Abstract. *Pedagogical skill is a built-in quality of a teacher, formation of professional skills of the teacher - ensures the high quality of his professional skills and knowledge.*

Keywords: *professional self-awareness, professional knowledge, qualification, pedagogical skills, professional ability, pedagogical etiquette, pedagogical technique.*

Introduction.

The main characteristics of pedagogical skill are: professional knowledge, qualification, skill, professional ability, pedagogical etiquette, pedagogical technique. The teacher's creative ability, innovative actions, qualification, physiological and mental quality coincide with pedagogical professional knowledge. Innovative creative energy develops in an infinite and continuous movement. In this pedagogical direction, the mutual influence of the teacher and the student, in mutual development, from cooperation to balance, to reach the highest level of development, is of great importance. Materialist dialectic is a continuous development in nature, reveals the unity, integrity and correspondence of scientific knowledge and experience.

In our opinion, pedagogical skill is an integrated quality of a teacher, because it includes in its composition interdependent, closely related units, that is, knowledge, business, abilities and qualities. Of course, since pedagogical skill is a complex structure, there are different approaches to its meaning and understanding. In accordance with modern demands, we conclude that the basis of pedagogical excellence is innovative activity. Only the desire for empathy, the continuous search, will lead the teacher to the highest level of his work. The citizens of our region, masters of their work, K. Nurgaliev, K. Bitibaeva, Zh. Shaijunusov, natives of our country R. Nurtazina, A. Iskakov, E. We made Ochkur criticism based on the activities of teachers. They reached the peak of their pedagogical activity based on the desire for innovation. However, innovative activity cannot be realized without professional knowledge and business skills and personal qualities. Especially nowadays, in order to achieve mastery, a teacher must be able to manage himself, he must have personal qualities such as optimism, leadership qualities, the ability to take risks, energy, and endurance. These qualities lead the teacher to empathy, motivates to create something new.

Research materials and methodology.

Education at school is one of the most important stages of a child's life. From which educational system and from which teacher he received education depends on the child's progress and personal development. The process of creation of professional skills considers not only the realization and formation of knowledge, but also its personality formation. Problems related to the professional skill of the teacher require many responsibilities. The ongoing reforms in general education and professional education schools in the Republic of Uzbekistan require fundamental changes in its pedagogical system. In the current period, the goals of education are changing, the content of educational information is being updated, pedagogical communication tools, and the object of pedagogical influence - students are also changing significantly. All these factors require

raising the level of pedagogical professionalism. A necessary condition for the renewal of the educational process is the improvement of the pedagogical skill of teachers, who are the main person of any pedagogical system. The formation of the teacher's professional skill in the new social context ensures the high quality of his professional skill and education. To the problems of developing general and professional skills of teachers N. Kuzmina, A. Shcherbakov paid attention. The modern education system complicates the problem of teachers' professional skills. Because right now, the general and spiritual culture of students is determined by the teacher. Pedagogical encyclopedia gives the following definition of pedagogical skill. As his name suggests, he loves children and constantly updates his upbringing and education at a high level.

Search results.

Content and importance of pedagogical skill, ways of formation.

The content of pedagogical skills, the humanistic direction of the teacher's personality. The art of education is one of the oldest and most complex arts. But it is not surprisingly simple, it starts with accepting and loving the student as he is. It is impossible to imagine the spiritual world of a person without an experienced teacher, he must master the ability to influence the student, form his needs and beliefs, abilities and practical skills. Pedagogical skill is a professional skill that optimizes all types of educational activities, directs them to the comprehensive development and improvement of an individual, the formation of his worldview abilities, and the need for socially important activities. Pedagogical skill is a set of personal qualities that ensure a high level of self-organization of professional pedagogical activities. The diversity and complexity of the tasks of forming a new person make the problems of pedagogical skills particularly relevant for modern educational theory and practice. Outstanding Russian scientist-pedagogue A.S. Makarenko said: "there is no control, no program can change the direction of the lesson determined by the composition of the lecturers." Unfortunately, there are no specific principles for achieving pedagogical excellence, but the modern concept of pedagogical excellence is primarily to create conditions for the development of creative abilities of future specialists, thanks to which scientific and professional pedagogical training can be achieved.

Interest in the problems of educational skills not only determined the optimal conditions for the comprehensive development of children, but also caused the difficulties faced by the educator on a daily basis. According to some statistical data, a teacher performs 258 types of work to prepare for lessons on new programs. It takes 4-5 hours to check the students' work. Self-service, duty, extracurricular activities take 10-12 hours per week. The teacher takes into account that his students are constantly changing, and he has to make decisions and act immediately. From a scientific and methodological point of view, these difficulties are usually created by establishing contact with children in any activity: study, organization, work, art, sports. It is often questioned whether the teacher is a phenomenon outside the system of tools and methods. Mastery is the power to seek aesthetics in the personality of the teacher? Why does the use of the same pedagogical tools and methods have positive results for some educators and the opposite for others? The teacher's skill is related to various theoretical, psychological-pedagogical, socio-psychological, philosophical knowledge and acts as a link between theory and practice, that is, between the educational system and the activity that leads to the change of existing activities. One of the main aspects of mastery is characterized by the ability to solve conflicts between theoretical ideas and the available fund of life requirements, accumulating knowledge and experience. As the experience of the masters of pedagogical work shows, the higher the skill of the teacher, the need

for additional education is associated with passing this level of pedagogical knowledge and moving to a higher level of theories and practices.

Discussions.

A master-pedagogical practice cannot disappear without a trace, cannot realize itself if it synthesizes the objective, cognitive, physical, and artistic capabilities of this generation. But experience is not given by itself. A reflection on the experience is provided. This idea, even in its initial form, as an assumption, is the initial theoretical knowledge, on the basis of which a detailed theoretical concept can be built. In order to achieve the secrets of professional skill, the teacher mainly improves the methods of education while teaching the student. With the help of these methods, students are educated in knowledge, skills, and behavioral relations. However, the methods used by teachers produce different results in the teaching process. It is clear that the work of an experienced master teacher gives quality results. And some teachers are unable to achieve minimal success even with tried and tested methods. "I do everything according to the methodical methodology, and the children make noise, do not listen, do not study. Why?", the teacher is upset. The preferences of students are not only influenced by the methods and tasks chosen by the teacher.

The success of a teacher's work often depends on his personality, character, relationship with students, and his skills. Master teachers constantly pay attention to the reaction caused by the student's actions. The skill of the teachers, explanation of the lessons, influence on the students makes them feel the joy of learning and makes sure that they can study well. For such teachers, the methods of teaching and education become a means of realizing the programmed qualities of the teacher's personality, a guide for students. A teacher can only teach his student what he knows. Therefore, pedagogical skill can be considered as a set of certain qualities of the teacher's personality. This is determined by his ability to optimally solve the pedagogical tasks of teaching, educating and developing students with a high level of psychological and pedagogical preparation. Pedagogical task is solved in a specific situation, it is taken into account in the study group and when choosing a special effect on students. First, it is a model of the problem situation. It, like any task, has a purpose, conditions and criteria for checking the effectiveness of its solution. A teacher is a master of these subjects, capable of making decisions without being programmed. We consider the pedagogical task as the teacher's formulation of how to act in unexpected situations. Its successful solution is checked by three main criteria:

1. With the condition of the learner at that moment;
2. Choosing a special method of influencing the student;
3. To understand that the pedagogical task needs to be searched before the teacher solves it.

What is a pedagogical task? Pedagogical task is to move to a new level when approaching the goal of pedagogical activity, to always understand the current pedagogical situation in order to change it. Pedagogical task can be considered as the main element of pedagogical skill, its solution shows the professional level of the teacher. All pedagogical activity consists of a series of pedagogical situations. Both the teacher and the students make them independently or specially. The teacher should be distinguished by his tolerance, patience, objectivity and sensitivity in any situation. He should always be able to monitor his actions and behavior in relations with students. The qualities of teachers, such as observation and ingenuity, the ability to use voice and diction, direct emotional impact on the student, as well as the ability to foresee the consequences of their actions, are of great importance. The teacher's skills are also reflected in his voice, speech rhythm,

gestures, and speech culture. In the case of the humanistic direction of the teacher's personality, orientation is carried out to create conditions for comprehensive development of the individual. In general, the concept of "humanism" means recognizing the value of a person as an individual, his right to free, full development and expression of his personal abilities. Pedagogical activity should have a humanistic orientation. This means that all actions of the teacher are subject to the specific interests of the child, student, and adult. Unlike the psychotherapist who communicates with the client, only in case of anxiety arising from his point of view and at the initiative of the client, the teacher should not only teach the other person, but also to some extent organize activities that predict the emergence of those conflicts and disagreements with the outside world. In this sense, the humanistic direction fully corresponds to the main tasks of pedagogy aimed at the individual. Helping a person to determine his attitude towards himself, other people, the world around him and his professional activities. However, any practical activity of a person is a manifestation of his intellectual, emotional and volitional spheres (internal behavior), which develops a certain daily and professional ideology, formed on the basis of certain principles and programs. Therefore, his principles, views, opinions, beliefs, needs are characterized by the content, tools and methods of his practical activity. Thus, the humanistic direction of the teacher's personality is the leading form of orientation. It determines the humanistic nature of professional activity, which is manifested in the understanding, development and implementation of the tasks of providing pedagogical assistance to students in their individual development and formation. The humanistic orientation of a person is formed on the basis of universal values (specific social definitions of the objects of the surrounding world that reveal a positive or negative meaning to a person and society: good, bad, kindness, cruelty).

The humanistic direction of the teacher's personality means treating the child as a high value, showing his freedom and free development abilities. A person can realize his creative possibilities for himself and the environment only if he has faith in himself. Not only his positive qualities, but also the whole individual, that is, when he is loved, respected for his dignity and shown humanity, is strengthened. In the modern pedagogical culture, which is a part of universal culture, progressive concepts that confirm the need to respect the individuality of the student, to recognize and protect his right to freedom and development, and humanistic and democratic principles of his upbringing and education have a proper place. The future teacher should actively participate in the process of professional self-awareness in order to form a humanistic direction of his personality from the first steps of mastering the profession, as this is one of the most important factors for the success of professional activity. At the same time, humanism is not an absolutization of forgiveness and submission to human imperfection. The teacher should make possible and reasonable requirements for the further development of the student, that is, he should implement a pedagogical influence of a humanistic, not authoritarian, nature. The humanistic meaning of pedagogical activity is characteristic of many teachers of all nations. In the middle of the 19th century, Adolf Disterweg, a famous German pedagogue and figure in the field of education, who was called the teacher of German teachers, put forward the universal goal of education: to serve truth, goodness, and beauty. "Each person and nation should be educated in a way of thinking called morality - this is striving for noble universal goals," he said. Outstanding teacher K.D. Ushinsky laid the theoretical foundations of national humanistic pedagogy. An ideal teacher, in his opinion, feels the mental state of his students, sees in them persons worthy of respect and recognition of their rights as adults. Such a teacher tries to create relationships where his mind,

morals, will, and character can have a personal impact on the personality of the student. In the new millennium, humanism becomes a generalized system of views, beliefs and ideals of the XXI century teacher. The content of its practical activity, its tools, methods and approaches are as follows:

- * the idea of a person-oriented approach to education and training;
- * subordinating all actions of the teacher to the real interests of the student;
- * helping the student to develop himself by educating himself, other people, nature, work;
- * ensuring the harmonious and creative development of each student, giving him the opportunity to show subjectivity and individuality;
- * widespread indirect use of pedagogical requirements (advice, inquiry, trust, approval, etc. pedagogical support);
- * gradual transition from group forms of interaction to individual;
- * emotional coloring of business relations with students;
- * constant control in the process of business relations;
- * overcoming various forms of authoritarianism, domination, sadism, teaching and upbringing from the life of society.

Conclusion

A teacher is a master of his work. This means a specialist with high culture, deep knowledge of his subject, well-acquainted with the fields of science and culture related to him, able to analyze psychological problems in a practical way, well-versed in the methodology of upbringing and education. Thus, the importance of pedagogical skills is shown as a set of personal qualities that ensure the highest level of organization of professional activities. These qualities include the humanistic orientation of the teacher's actions, professional knowledge, pedagogical features and pedagogical techniques. In science, there is also an understanding that what a teacher needs to master is pedagogical technology. Pedagogical understanding is the mastery of methods and methods that influence students. At the same time, to master some techniques of art, to know the methods of speech, relaxation, raising the voice, facial expressions. If a child finds himself in a difficult situation with a drug addict, criminal or alcoholic, the teacher must be able to communicate with them and not just talk, but also convince and influence them. A. S. about the skill of the teacher. Makarenko wrote: I reached such a level of mastery without even believing in the existence of mastery.!! Or was it possible to talk about pedagogical talent? How many talented pupils do we have? And why should a child in the hands of an untalented teacher suffer? Can we educate children on demand? No. About real knowledge, about being able to educate. What brings a beginning teacher to mastery? Pedagogical literature answers this question in one sense - pedagogical techniques and efforts.

In other words, to be able to understand the student, that is, to know the psychology of communication, to know the peculiarities of speech, to know how your words are perceived by students, to be able to control oneself, to know the ability to behave. Experience shows that no inquiry and no survey can replace the conversation between a teacher and a student, a teacher and a student. In this process, the information conversation is dominated by the teacher. In this case, the conversation breaks down and misunderstandings arise. The school teacher does not take into account his psychological influence on the student. A teacher should be able to find a way for every child. Whether the child is withdrawn or mischievous, lazy or apathetic. The teacher should remember his one word to the child, i.e., a satisfying word, so that it plays an important role in the

child's life and is memorized forever. In conclusion, reaching a new field of school education in accordance with today's requirements is closely related to the teacher's kindness, knowledge, and skills. Only a teacher who is devoted to his profession can master teaching ethics, teaching technique, and skill.

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